

Are atomic tests for ER=EPR valid?

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Abstract

We raise questions about the meaningfulness of proposed tests of the ER=EPR conjecture. In our view it is important to pin down what the poetic koan really means.

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1 Introduction

This paper argues for deflating a recent claim casting doubt, or severe limits, on the extent of the ER=EPR conjecture [1]. It is important to note “ER=EPR” is a conjectured correspondence, not an equality [2].

“ER=EPR” also means something very different in AdS spacetimes (not our cosmos) to what it might mean in FRLW spacetimes (our cosmos). There are already proposed tests for that fictional physics [3], some of which are moot, since they are tests we can never perform. But among those tests there may be some that could be done in our universe, depending on the lifetimes of entangled particles (the actual geometric ER-bridge). Entanglement is stochastic, not geometric, and may persist while the ER-bridge initially formed has already collapsed and the entanglement reformed elsewhere. This poses great difficulties for the proposed tests. Well-controlled quantum computer circuits might be the best laboratory setting for such tests, not so much atomic spectroscopy, which is “hot & messy.”

We will presume the paper of Javed & Wilson-Ewing [1] is considering local spacetime cobordism regions in FRLW. In which case the meaning of ER=EPR is not really that well understood, and may not support the threading of electromagnetic fields lines that their paper presupposes.

We take a perhaps fresh approach to the meaning of ER=EPR, which is in the context of topological 4-geon theory (T4G theory) — a speculative but conservative minimalist gravitational theory of quantum mechanics (see reviews [4, 5]).

T4G theory would agree with Barandes’ Indivisible Stochastic QM formulation [6] if we discard *need to know* the interior of the spacetime cobordism. This is however inadequate for assessing claims made about interpretations of what “ER=EPR” means, because the ER-bridge side involves the cobordism interiors, while the EPR side of the correspondence is only definable using stochastic boundary data. For an adequate account of ER=EPR we insist one needs a functorial correspondence, and take steps in theorizing to avoid category confusions.

Thus before anything salient can be said about the ER=EPR correspondence one should first establish a map between the two categories, as suggested in the papers [7, 8], which we will take as read.

1.1 Topological 4-geon framing

In T4G theory we distinguish QM/QFT from Gravity by categorical distinction. Gravity is the theory of the bulk interior cobordism, including the boundary data, while QM/QFT is taken to be explicitly only a theory of transformation of one boundary to the other, represented here symbolically as a real cobordism mapping

$$\mathfrak{C} : \Sigma_1 \longrightarrow \Sigma_2,$$

and the data on the boundaries has to be abstract, and best thought of in the form of probability amplitude scaled Clifford rotors [4]. By extending to a doubled space-time algebra (STA) in the form $\mathbb{C}l_8$ we can incorporate the entire LR-symmetric Standard Model, with three generations, and *no more* [5, 9–11].

For T4G theory, it is in the category of the mapping data that we employ complexified spinors. These are abstractions, explicitly statistical descriptors, not elements of real spacetime. Indeed, it is the wormhole topology that forces T4G to use complexification, in the form of an explicit bipartite structure in the model, whereby the real spacetime algebra (STA) has to include a $Cl_{0,2}$ structure,

$$(STA) \quad Cl_{3,1} \xrightarrow{\text{extended}} Cl_{0,2} \otimes Cl_{3+3,1+1} \cong Cl_{6,2} \cong Cl_8.$$

This is a relatively unexplored model, especially in terms of geometrodynamics. It is our contention that what can be transported or “teleported” across the minimal T4G-wormholes is not entirely obvious, and it is plausible only Clifford frame orientation (spin numbers) and gravitational wave momenta might be topologically admissible transport quantities, not necessarily Standard Model charge. Transport of charge units implies boson propagation¹ through the putative wormholes, and that could always collapse the ER-bridge, and at least classically is a known result of GR topological censorship [12]. On the other hand (and what makes life interesting one could say) topology changes would seem inevitable [13] if degenerate but well-behaved metrics play any role in quantum gravity.

The reason charge transport can collapse ER-bridge structure is not just that charge transport implies energy transport, but is more direct in T4G theory, since the electroweak charge is given by the eigenvalues of the Cartan diagonals in the $\mathbb{C}l_8$ algebra, which are bipartite spacetime algebra operators/transforms, algebraically constructed from spacetime algebra spinor monomials [5]. There is as yet no explicit geometrodynamics for this “charge from spacetime topology” account, but we must bare this in mind in any serious discussions of hypothetical ER=EPR transport processes.

Although we will not pursue another criticism of the proposed test of ER=EPR, it is worth noting that topological censorship [12] is a compelling reason to suspect nothing we can detect can alert us to the existence of these minimal wormholes, as argued by Bao et al [14], QM forbids non-destructive detection of entanglement, and that turns out to be equivalent to topological censorship if we grant that there

¹As it were: the bosonic fields are abstract stochastic descriptors in T4G theory, and what *charge* is transported — if anything — is an actual photon, *W* particle, or gluon.

is some sort of ER=EPR correspondence. Atomic spectroscopy should not be an exception to these QM constraints.

2 Does hydrogen spectroscopy test ER=EPR?

Javed and Wilson-Ewing have proposed an interesting phenomenological test of ER=EPR using the hydrogen atom [1]. Their argument is not, however, a direct test of the ER=EPR conjecture in its more bare-bones structural form. It is a test of an additional dynamical hypothesis: namely that part of the electric field sourced by an entangled charged particle enters the hypothetical corresponding microscopic wormhole and is therefore removed from the exterior Coulomb field.

Any such dynamical effects have to be very carefully scrutinized before claims about “no-go” results can be accepted. We find that interpreting their calculations as any sort of refutation of the ER=EPR conjecture to be highly premature. One may even be more optimistic about ER=EPR, because it is desirable to have strong constraints on what transport features are permitted. These may help us pin-down the likely physical–geometric topology. For example, the (unpublished?) speculation has always been that only minimal Planck area wormhole throats are stable. Consider as well that entanglement itself, via the actual physical geometry, is highly transportable, owing to the ubiquitous vacuum entanglement implied by most accounts of QFT’s. Which is a way of saying EPRB correlation experiments have to very carefully engineer sufficiently isolated Bell pairs to prevent entanglement transport with the environment up until the desired measurements are made.

In their notation, Javed & Wilson–Ewing consider an entangled charged particle of charge q_e to have assigned a modified Gauss law,

$$\frac{q_e}{\epsilon_0} = \oint_S \mathbf{E}_S \cdot d\mathbf{a} + \oint_W \mathbf{E}_W \cdot d\mathbf{a},$$

and the observable exterior field is parametrized by

$$\mathbf{E}_S = \frac{q_e}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + s/(\pi\alpha^2)} \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \quad (1)$$

where s is the entanglement entropy and α is a phenomenological strength parameter. This leads to an effective suppression of the electron charge,

$$e \longmapsto e' = \frac{e}{1 + s/(\pi\alpha^2)}, \quad (2)$$

and hence to shifts in the hydrogen spectrum, including the hyperfine splitting. Such shifts are not observed, from which they obtain strong lower bounds on α .

The conclusion is best stated conditionally:

If ER=EPR implies exterior electromagnetic flux loss through microscopic wormholes of the form (1), then hydrogen spectroscopy places severe bounds on the amplitude of that flux-loss effect.

This is not equivalent to:

Hydrogen spectroscopy refutes ER=EPR.

The latter conclusion would require the flux-loss hypothesis to be a necessary consequence of ER=EPR. It is not. In the topological 4-geon formulation, and more

generally in any sufficiently conservative form of ER=EPR, the Einstein-Rosen side and the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen side are not identical objects. The relation is not a literal equality between a classical electromagnetic field configuration and a classical wormhole geometry. It is a correspondence between two *different* descriptions of the same microscopic channel: a bulk cobordism description and a boundary stochastic-transform description. The appropriate mathematical structure is therefore functorial, not an identity of observables.

2.1 How is electric field lost?

Another assumption of Javed and Wilson–Ewing that requires closer scrutiny is their claim that, if the proton is treated as too large to be affected but the electron is treated as point-like, then an entangled hydrogen atom can acquire an effective non-zero charge because part of the electron’s electric field is lost into a non-traversable wormhole. Their proposal is not meaningless, but it is considerably stronger than ER=EPR itself:

“Under the assumption that the proton (being much larger than the quantum gravity scale) does not lose any of its electric field into the wormhole, but that the electron (assumed to be a point particle) does, if the ER=EPR wormhole is non-traversable, then the effective total charge of the hydrogen atom will not vanish when the proton and electron are entangled, due to the loss of some of the electron’s electric field into the wormhole. ”

What would it mean for electric flux to enter a bridge?

In an ordinary Maxwell description, “loss of electric field” cannot mean that electric field is a conserved substance which is physically depleted. Electric field is not a particle number, and a static Coulomb field is not a collection of countable real photons. Rather, the proposal of [1] should be read, in our opinion, as a claim about electric flux: an observer who surrounds the electron by a closed surface in the accessible exterior region is assumed to measure less outward electric flux than would ordinarily be associated with charge $-e$. The missing flux is then assigned to an inaccessible wormhole component.

That is a definite model of how a bridge might modify the electromagnetic constraint seen by an exterior observer. But it is an additional model assumption. ER=EPR by itself, in T4G theory, says that a non-product microscopic cobordism channel can induce a non-factorizing boundary transform. It does not say that the same channel changes the exterior electromagnetic coupling of one member of an entangled pair, nor that it changes that coupling asymmetrically for an electron and a proton.

For hydrogen the usual atomic Coulomb field is already an effective description reconstructed from the quantum state of the bound system. It is not necessary to picture that field as a set of literal flux lines continuously extending from the electron to the proton. The observable issue is instead whether the effective boundary description of an entangled atomic state predicts a modified Coulomb interaction or a modified total charge. A charge-preserving T4G correspondence need not predict either.

The electron’s spatial probability distribution also cannot be treated as a minor technicality. Atomic electrons do have non-zero probability density in the nuclear

region for the orbitals relevant to electron capture. In particular, s -state wavefunctions are non-zero at the nucleus, while relativistic $p_{1/2}$ states may also possess non-vanishing nuclear overlap. Orbital electron capture provides direct physical evidence that this overlap is not merely a formal feature of the wavefunction: the capture rate depends on the bound-electron density in the nuclear region [15].

Orthodox quantum mechanics does not require wormhole topology in order to describe this overlap or the resulting atomic correlations, however, T4G makes the stronger ontological proposal that primitive, un-averaged entanglement must have a wormhole-like topological representative in the real spacetime bulk [4, 7]. The reason is structural: in a pure spacetime-algebra ontology, a genuinely bipartite microscopic relation cannot be represented as an additional elementary field substance (since there is no postulated such ‘substance’ available). It must instead be represented by non-trivial spacetime connectivity. In this sense, primitive bipartite structure implies non-trivial bulk topology.

This claim does not imply that every entanglement measure assigned to an atom identifies one primitive electron–proton ER bridge. The atomic state is a coarse-grained boundary description of a composite system involving the electron, the confined constituents of the proton, electromagnetic interactions, and usually further environmental degrees of freedom. Electron–proton entanglement in such a description is physically meaningful, but it need not be a pure two-endpoint EPR resource. Rather, it may be the effective statistical image of a larger and dynamically changing ensemble of elementary microscopic channels.

Monogamy reinforces this distinction without forbidding electron–proton entanglement altogether. An elementary electron cannot freely sustain independent maximal bipartite entanglement with arbitrarily many other degrees of freedom. Its correlations must be distributed among the proton’s constituents, electromagnetic interaction channels, and any environmental systems with which the atom becomes correlated [16, 17]. Therefore a calculation that begins with an effective atomic entanglement entropy cannot immediately replace it by a single stable wormhole throat attached to the electron.

Accordingly, the distinction between a pointlike electron whose field leaks into a bridge and a composite proton whose field does not leak cannot be justified merely by comparing their nominal sizes. A proper derivation would require a microscopic dynamical calculation: one would need to specify the elementary bridge-channel ensemble, determine how it coarse-grains to the electron–proton boundary state, and derive its coupling to the effective Dirac–Maxwell interaction. Entanglement dynamics in open and composite quantum systems has of course been extensively studied [18, 19], but this particular bulk-topological-to-atomic-electromagnetic calculation has not, to our knowledge, been supplied by the ER=EPR flux-leakage proposal.

The hydrogen state is a coupled quantum system, and its effective electromagnetic description is determined by the joint boundary state. To infer an entanglement-dependent reduction of the electron’s exterior charge requires an additional microscopic rule specifying how the relevant bridge channels modify the Dirac–Maxwell coupling. No such rule follows from ER=EPR alone.

3 The categorical form of ER=EPR

The claim that ER=EPR should be understood functorially needs to be made more explicit than the usual slogan permits. The putative wormhole and an entangled state are not literally the same mathematical object. A wormhole is a real four-dimensional spacetime topology, while an entangled quantum state is a statistical descriptor of correlations in boundary measurements.

3.1 What the ER=EPR map is supposed to mean

For T4G theory, the relevant distinction is between a category of real spacetime cobordisms and a category of abstract boundary transformations. The former contains the gravitational bulk histories; the latter contains the stochastic Clifford-rotor data by which boundary observers represent those histories.

Let $\mathbf{Cob}^{\text{micro}}$ denote the tentative category whose objects are admissible three-dimensional boundary hypersurfaces together with their allowed physical boundary data,

$$(\Sigma, \mathcal{D} * \Sigma).$$

A morphism in this category is a real four-dimensional cobordism region,

$$\mathfrak{C} : (\Sigma_1, \mathcal{D}_{\Sigma_1}) \longrightarrow (\Sigma_2, \mathcal{D}_{\Sigma_2}),$$

whose boundary is formed from an initial hypersurface Σ_1 , a final hypersurface Σ_2 , and any additional timelike or asymptotic boundary pieces required by the physical situation. The notation

$$\mathfrak{C} : \Sigma_1 \longrightarrow \Sigma_2$$

therefore does not mean that Σ_1 is continuously deformed into Σ_2 . It means that \mathfrak{C} is a real spacetime region having Σ_1 and Σ_2 as its incoming and outgoing boundaries.

If two cobordism regions can be joined along a common boundary,

$$\mathfrak{C}_{12} : \Sigma_1 \longrightarrow \Sigma_2, \quad \mathfrak{C}_{23} : \Sigma_2 \longrightarrow \Sigma_3,$$

then they can be composed by gluing,

$$\mathfrak{C}_{23} \circ \mathfrak{C}_{12} : \Sigma_1 \longrightarrow \Sigma_3.$$

This composition is simply the larger real spacetime region obtained by joining the exit boundary of the first history to the entry boundary of the second.

The boundary description is different. Let $\mathbf{Stoch}^{\text{bdry}} * \mathcal{C}\ell$ denote a category whose objects are spaces of abstract boundary descriptors. In the present T4G setting these descriptors are probability-amplitude-scaled Clifford rotors, or equivalent spinorial data, assigned to a boundary hypersurface:

$$\Psi * \Sigma \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma).$$

They are not assumed to be literal fields inhabiting the real bulk spacetime. They are boundary data used to calculate the probabilities of possible future boundary records, and crucially with an algebra that supports in stochastic transition terms [6], single-particle self-interference.

A morphism in $\mathbf{Stoch}^{\text{bdry}} * \mathcal{C}\ell$ is a stochastic boundary transformation,

$$T * \mathfrak{C} : \mathcal{B}(\Sigma_1) \longrightarrow \mathcal{B}(\Sigma_2).$$

Operationally, $T_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is the effective transition rule inferred by an observer who knows the incoming boundary data but does not resolve the interior topology of \mathfrak{C} . In the simplest notation,

$$\Psi_{\Sigma_2} = T_{\mathfrak{C}}(\Psi_{\Sigma_1}).$$

More generally, the transformation specifies conditional probabilities for possible outgoing boundary records:

$$P_{\mathfrak{C}}(b_2 | b_1),$$

where b_1 and b_2 label allowed boundary outcomes on Σ_1 and Σ_2 . This is the sense in which the boundary theory is stochastic. It does not assert that the bulk cobordism is itself unreal or stochastic. Rather, the stochasticity arises because the boundary observer does not retain a complete description of the real gravitational–interior channel structure.

The proposed ER=EPR correspondence is then a map

$$\mathcal{F} : \mathbf{Cob}^{\text{micro}} * 4 \longrightarrow \mathbf{Stoch}^{\text{bdry}} * \mathcal{C}\ell, \quad (3)$$

with the following meaning:

$$\mathcal{F}(\Sigma, \mathcal{D}_{\Sigma}) = \mathcal{B}(\Sigma),$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathfrak{C}) = T_{\mathfrak{C}}.$$

Thus \mathcal{F} maps a real bulk cobordism channel to the effective stochastic transformation which it induces between its two boundaries.

Calling \mathcal{F} a functor means that it respects the physical operation of joining histories. If two bulk regions are glued,

$$\mathfrak{C}_{12} \circ \mathfrak{C}_{23},$$

then their boundary transformations must compose to $\Sigma_1 \rightarrow \Sigma_3$, in the corresponding order:

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathfrak{C}_{12} \circ \mathfrak{C}_{23}) = \mathcal{F}(\mathfrak{C}_{12}) \circ \mathcal{F}(\mathfrak{C}_{23}),$$

or equivalently,

$$T_{\mathfrak{C}_{12} \circ \mathfrak{C}_{23}} = T_{\mathfrak{C}_{12}} \circ T_{\mathfrak{C}_{23}}. \quad (4)$$

This ordering of composition is a primitive notion of “causality.” It also satisfies a generalization of the principle of general covariance: that *if we carry out a transformation on each object individually, then this is the same as carrying out the transformation on the whole object.* (This was first articulated by Lasenby to the best of our knowledge [20].)

Equation (4) should not be construed as mere schematic notation. It is the consistency condition required if a boundary observer is to describe a longer physical history by successively composing the transformations associated with shorter real spacetime regions.

The real spacetime cobordism is not an uncertain stochastic process, the uncertainty and necessity of a stochastic boundary description is the scientific observer’s model limitation, not Natures. But this is not an appeal to mysticism nor Idealism, it is just a practical constraint on our own laboratory data gathering capacities.

Nor does this mean we can defeat Heisenberg Uncertainty (HUP), which is definitely not contradicted by T4G spacetime realism [4, 8]. The reason (in brief) why the HUP still holds is because in a T4G cobordism one cannot time-evolve the data on the boundary Σ_1 to deduce the configurations on the boundary Σ_2 in any space-time where the cobordism interior is indivisible (non-factorizable), and that derives from spacetime cobordisms occupying equivalence classes of compatible boundary measurement set-ups and detections [4, 8, 21, 22].

We may now state the ER=EPR claim more carefully. Consider two elementary boundary systems, labelled A and B . If they have no relevant common bulk channel, their joint boundary evolution should be describable by independent transformations,

$$T_{AB} = T_A \otimes T_B. \quad (5)$$

Here T_A evolves the boundary data associated with A , T_B evolves the boundary data associated with B , and \otimes means that the joint rule contains no additional correlation beyond the two separately specified rules.

By contrast, suppose that the relevant microscopic cobordism contains a non-product bridge channel,

$$\mathfrak{C}_{AB}^{\text{bridge}} : \Sigma_{1,A} \sqcup \Sigma_{1,B} \longrightarrow \Sigma_{2,A} \sqcup \Sigma_{2,B}.$$

The symbol \sqcup means that the two boundary components are initially distinct. The claim is that the bridge topology prevents the corresponding boundary transformation from factorizing:

$$T_{AB} = \mathcal{F}(\mathfrak{C}_{AB}^{\text{bridge}}) \neq T_A \otimes T_B. \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is the EPR side of the correspondence. It says that the probabilities of the two boundary outcomes cannot be computed as though A and B had separately evolved independently. The observed correlation is therefore statistical and is encoded in the joint boundary transformation.

The ER side is not the non-factorizing transformation itself. It is the real bulk feature which gives rise to it:

$$\mathfrak{C}_{AB}^{\text{bridge}} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}} T_{AB} \neq T_A \otimes T_B. \quad (7)$$

This is the precise sense in which T4G interprets ER=EPR. A microscopic Einstein–Rosen bridge is a non-product cobordism channel in the real bulk; an Einstein–Podolsky–Rosen correlation is the non-factorization of the stochastic boundary transformation obtained after the interior channel has been hidden from the boundary description.

The correspondence therefore does not *directly* identify a wormhole with a correlation function, an entanglement entropy, an electromagnetic field line, or a classical geometric throat of measurable macroscopic size. It relates two descriptions at different categorical levels. The bulk description contains real cobordism topology. The boundary description contains the stochastic Clifford-rotor transformation induced by that topology. This distinction will be central below, because a constraint on a particular classical-field model of wormhole flux leakage need not constrain the more basic correspondence (7).

This distinction is crucial. The EPR side is statistical. It consists of correlations in the probabilities assigned to boundary events. The ER side is gravitational-topological. It consists of microscopic connectivity in the bulk channel ensemble. Therefore ER=EPR cannot be tested by assuming that a classical electromagnetic field literally flows through the same bridge unless one first supplies an additional dynamical principle saying that the functor (3) maps gauge flux into bulk throat flux. No such principle follows from ER=EPR alone.

In the topological 4-geon interpretation, the minimal claim is instead

bulk microscopic bridge \Rightarrow boundary non-factorizing stochastic transform,

not

bulk microscopic bridge \Rightarrow macroscopic electromagnetic flux leakage.

The latter is a much stronger phenomenological ansatz. It may be worth testing, but it should not be identified with ER=EPR itself.

3.2 Why field leakage is not implied by ER=EPR

The hydrogen argument assumes that a portion of the electron’s electric field enters the microscopic wormhole and thereby weakens the exterior Coulomb interaction. This is a classical-field picture. It treats the Coulomb field as if it were a substance whose flux lines can be diverted into an additional geometric opening. That picture is not forced by a quantum-cobordism account of entanglement.

In a quantum theory, the Coulomb interaction in hydrogen is not fundamentally a literal stream of classical electric flux passing continuously between electron and proton. It is the long-wavelength effective description of photon exchange, gauge constraints, and boundary amplitudes. It is therefore very dubious whether the electromagnetic flux concept has any meaning at the level of T4G minimal wormhole structures. One would be talking about statistical averages over many ensembles, and that raises the question of whether there exists a well-defined average for an elementary fundamental process like minimal ER-bridge transport. To gain statistics for a semi-classical field description one must first have at least one event being possible. But wormhole traversals are surely processes with fundamental thresholds, requiring violation of the null or weak energy conditions [12, 23].

In topological 4-geon theory, the bulk ontology contains microscopic topology-changing channels and Standard-Model events; the boundary observer reconstructs fields as effective, coarse-grained descriptions of many unresolved channels. Thus the classical electric field is not a primitive object that must enter an ER bridge. It is an “emergent” boundary field.

The relevant distinction is

boundary Coulomb field \neq bulk flux substance.

The Coulomb field belongs to the effective boundary theory. The ER bridge belongs to the microscopic bulk channel structure. A functor from bulk cobordisms to boundary transforms need not preserve a classical field-line picture, because field lines are not objects in the microscopic cobordism category.

Moreover, for a non-traversable ER bridge, the assumption of electromagnetic flux transport is especially strong. Non-traversability means that the bridge does

not provide an operational channel for signals or charges. A model in which exterior Gauss-law flux is removed from one asymptotic region and hidden in an inaccessible wormhole must explain why this does not amount to a modification of the gauge constraint itself. In ordinary gauge theory, Gauss law is not merely a dynamical equation; it is a constraint associated with gauge redundancy and charge conservation. Therefore a suppression of the observable charge,

$$e \mapsto e', \quad e' \neq e,$$

is not a generic prediction of entanglement. It is a model-dependent violation, or effective deformation, of the usual boundary Gauss constraint.

A conservative ER=EPR model should not allow the electron's gauge charge to become an entanglement-dependent quantity. In the Javed–Wilson–Ewing model the exterior Coulomb field is effectively weakened by replacing

$$e \mapsto e' = \frac{e}{1 + s/(\pi\alpha^2)}, \quad (8)$$

where s is the entanglement entropy of the relevant bipartite state. This is the step that produces the hydrogenic energy shifts and the apparent non-neutrality of hydrogen.

The difficulty is that this replacement is not a consequence of ER=EPR itself. In the usual Dirac-Maxwell coupling, the electric charge is the coefficient of the electromagnetic coupling to the charged spinor current. In spacetime-algebra notation one may write the current schematically as

$$J = \tilde{\psi}\gamma_0\psi,$$

so that the electromagnetic interaction is controlled by the charged current

$$j = qJ.$$

For an electron, $q = -e$.

Entanglement may change the joint state in which the electron participates, and hence may change the correlation structure of boundary transition probabilities. But it does not, by itself, change the charge label multiplying the electron current:

$$j_e = -e\tilde{\psi}\gamma_0\psi \text{ is not } \longrightarrow j_e = -e(s)\tilde{\psi}\gamma_0\psi.$$

Thus in our view the ER=EPR claim, in its conservative form, is only a claim about non-factorization of the joint boundary transform, not a claim that the local gauge coupling of an elementary charged state is renormalized by its entanglement entropy.

This is the point at which the hydrogen argument adds an extra physical assumption. It assumes that the microscopic bridge removes a fraction of the electromagnetic flux from the exterior region, and that the boundary observer may therefore replace the electron charge by (8). But a charge-preserving ER=EPR model need not make this replacement. It may instead hold fixed the charge carried by the electron current while allowing the two-particle transition kernel to become non-factorizing:

$$K(a, b \rightarrow a', b') \neq K_A(a \rightarrow a')K_B(b \rightarrow b').$$

The bridge then appears in the boundary theory as a correlation structure, not as a reduction of the electron's Coulomb charge.

Consequently, the hydrogen calculation constrains the additional hypothesis

$$\text{entanglement} \Rightarrow \text{exterior electromagnetic flux loss} \Rightarrow e \mapsto e',$$

rather than a more passive ER=EPR correspondence functorial relation. A topological 4-geon version of ER=EPR could or should therefore impose

$$q_e = -e$$

as a fixed label of the electron channel, while allowing the joint two-particle channel to be non-product. With this charge-preserving condition, the Coulomb field reconstructed by the boundary observer is not weakened merely because the electron is entangled, and the hydrogen spectroscopy bound no longer applies to ER=EPR as such.

Microscopic bridge structure may alter correlations between boundary events, but it need not renormalize the total exterior charge of an electron in an entanglement-dependent way. If charge conservation is imposed functorially, then the hydrogen neutrality constraint used by Javed and Wilson-Ewing is automatically evaded, because their effective charge shift (2) is simply not a prediction of the theory.

Other ideas loosely associated with the original ER=EPR conjecture seem to be of appeal, such as threading electric field lines through a quantum wormhole [24], but such models are semi-classical, and so of highly dubious usage since they violate the spirit of the T4G version of ER=EPR, which is distinctly non-classical and non-semi-classical (there is no electromagnetic field line to thread with, there are only photons).

We may be wrong of course, but to-date the only wormhole traversability T4G theory requires would be that of isotropic spin correlations [25, 26], and in the ER-bridge category that would correspond to something like torsion, or reorientation mapping as we trace geodesics through the minimal T4G wormholes. None of this is well-established geometrodynamics, so it is impossible to make any claims about what other physical influences could be transported through the ER=EPR wormholes in the T4G context. Our only guide is the unphysical models obtained from AdS-CFT correspondences [27] but with the promise of laboratory tests of a different nature to those proposed by Javed and Wilson-Ewing, for example quantum teleportation [28, 29].

3.3 Composite systems and the status of hydrogenic entanglement

There is also a conceptual ambiguity in treating hydrogen as a primitive ER=EPR pair. The hydrogen atom is a composite bound system. Its proton is not elementary, and its electronic state is not a pair of isolated point particles joined by a single clean Bell-type channel. Standard quantum mechanics certainly allows entanglement between composite subsystems, and one should not deny that such Hilbert-space entanglement exists. However, such entanglement is not automatically a primitive ER bridge in the microscopic bulk category.

The distinction is between kinematical Hilbert-space entanglement and primitive cobordism-channel entanglement. A bipartite state of two composite systems,

$$\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B,$$

may fail to factorize. But if

$$A = A_1 A_2 \cdots A_N, \quad B = B_1 B_2 \cdots B_M,$$

then the microscopic ER structure, if present, need not be a single bridge connecting A to B . It may be a network, sum, or rapidly fluctuating ensemble of elementary channels:

$$W_{AB}^{\text{eff}} = \sum_{\Gamma} w_{\Gamma} W_{\Gamma},$$

where each W_{Γ} is a microscopic channel graph connecting elementary degrees of freedom. The *effective* entanglement of the composite systems is then a boundary coarse-graining of the elementary channel ensemble.

This matters for hydrogen. The proton is a confined QCD bound state. Its charge is distributed among quark and gluonic degrees of freedom, with confinement preventing any naive identification of the proton with a single point-like elementary endpoint. Therefore the statement

electron entangled with proton \Rightarrow one electron–proton wormhole

is not a necessary consequence of ER=EPR. A more faithful microscopic statement would be

electron–proton boundary entanglement \Rightarrow non-factorizing sum over elementary bulk channels.

Such a sum need not act as a single geometric throat capable of absorbing a fixed fraction of the electron’s exterior Coulomb flux.

The same point applies to orbital or centre-of-mass entanglement in hydrogen. The usual separation into center-of-mass and relative coordinates produces correlations between the electron and proton coordinates. But these correlations are partly artefacts of the chosen tensor factorization. They are not operationally equivalent to a prepared Bell pair of two elementary particles. Therefore it is hazardous to infer from ordinary hydrogenic coordinate entanglement that every hydrogen atom contains a stable microscopic wormhole with a throat area proportional to that entanglement measure.

A topological 4-geon formulation should therefore distinguish three levels:

1. elementary channel entanglement \longleftrightarrow primitive microscopic ER bridge,
2. composite-system entanglement \longleftrightarrow coarse-grained channel network,
3. field-mode entanglement \longleftrightarrow boundary statistical non-factorization.

Only the first level is a candidate for a simple one-bridge ER=EPR correspondence. The second and third levels require coarse-graining and are not expected to produce the same phenomenology as a single elementary bridge.

3.4 Monogamy and the transience of microscopic bridges

A further issue is that entanglement is dynamically fragile. The hydrogen analysis effectively treats entanglement as if it generated a persistent geometric structure whose effect on the electron’s Coulomb field is time-independent. This is not the natural interpretation in a microscopic cobordism theory.

Entanglement is constrained by monogamy. In its familiar three-qubit form, the entanglement shared by a subsystem A with B and with C obeys a trade-off: maximal bipartite entanglement of A with B excludes independent maximal bipartite entanglement of A with C [16]. More generally, the extent and precise form of monogamy depend on the entanglement measure and the multipartite system under consideration [17].

Accordingly, in a many-body environment the bipartite entanglement associated with a given elementary degree of freedom is not generally an immutable two-body resource. It may be redistributed among environmental and interaction degrees of freedom as the total state evolves. A primitive ER bridge, if it is taken to correspond to an elementary EPR relation, should therefore be interpreted as a conditional microscopic channel associated with the relevant joint state, rather than as a permanent classical handle attached to a particle.

The appropriate object for a composite atomic system is not a single fixed wormhole geometry, but a coarse-grained ensemble of microscopic channel histories. Schematically, for a boundary transition from state i to state f ,

$$T_{fi} = \sum_{W \in \mathcal{C}_{fi}} \mu(W), \exp\left(\frac{iS[W]}{\hbar}\right). \quad (9)$$

Here \mathcal{C}_{fi} is the class of admissible microscopic cobordism channels compatible with the specified boundary preparation and boundary record, $S[W]$ is the action associated with the channel W , and $\mu(W)$ is its statistical weight. Equation (9) does not deny that an elementary EPR relation has a real geometric representative in the bulk. On the contrary, in T4G the elementary bridge is a genuine topological feature of the microscopic spacetime history. The point is that an atomic state does not normally isolate one such elementary bridge as a persistent semi-classical object.

Hydrogen is a composite, interacting, and environmentally embedded system. The electron, the proton's confined constituents, emitted and virtual photons, and external preparation apparatus contribute to the effective boundary state. The entanglement attributed to the atomic electron-proton split is therefore a coarse-grained statistical property of this larger channel ensemble. It need not correspond to one identifiable elementary ER bridge, still less to a stable throat with a time-independent area.

This distinction also changes the meaning of an “area” inferred from entanglement. In semi-classical black-hole examples, an entropy–area relation can refer to a geometrically distinguished horizon or throat. In an atomic setting, however, an entropy-like quantity associated with a chosen bipartition is at most evidence for non-factorization of the effective boundary transform. It is not by itself a measurement of the area of a single bulk bridge. One might introduce an effective bookkeeping quantity,

$$A_{\text{eff}} \sim \ell_{\text{Pl}}^2 I(A : B),$$

where $I(A : B)$ is an appropriate mutual-information measure, but this would characterize the coarse-grained correlation structure of the boundary description. It would not license the inference that a definite fraction of a classical Maxwell field is diverted through a definite microscopic throat.

The hydrogen analysis therefore combines two distinct levels of description. It begins from an effective, coarse-grained atomic entanglement measure, but

then treats the inferred ER structure as though it were a single persistent semiclassical wormhole with an independently specified classical flux response. That identification is not entailed by ER=EPR, and it is particularly inappropriate in T4G, where elementary bridges are real microscopic geometrical channels whereas composite-system entanglement is the stochastic boundary signature of an unresolved ensemble of such channels.

4 A charge-preserving ER=EPR alternative

One can formulate a charge-preserving alternative that retains the core ER=EPR idea while eliminating the flux-leakage phenomenology. Let \mathcal{C}_{AB} denote the class of microscopic bridge channels associated with two boundary degrees of freedom A and B . The ER=EPR claim is that the boundary transition kernel has the form

$$K(a, b \rightarrow a', b') = \sum_{W \in \mathcal{C}_{AB}} \mu(W) K_W(a, b \rightarrow a', b'),$$

and that this kernel is not generally divisible:

$$K(a, b \rightarrow a', b') \neq K_A(a \rightarrow a') K_B(b \rightarrow b').$$

The gauge constraint is imposed separately:

$$Q_A + Q_B = Q'_A + Q'_B,$$

and, for an isolated electron,

$$Q_e = -e$$

in every admissible channel. In such a model the bridge changes the correlation structure of the boundary transform but does not change the electron's charge. Hence

$$e' = e$$

rather than (2). The Coulomb spectrum and hydrogen neutrality are then unchanged at the level tested by Javed and Wilson-Ewing.

This is the conservative expectation if gauge charge is a superselection label, or Clifford generator-diagonal eigenvalue [5], on the boundary category. The functor (3) should preserve the relevant charge labels:

$$\mathcal{F}(W) : \mathcal{H}_{q_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{q_2} \longrightarrow \mathcal{H}_{q_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{q_2},$$

not

$$\mathcal{F}(W) : \mathcal{H}_{q_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{q_2} \longrightarrow \mathcal{H}_{q'_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{q_2}, \quad q'_1 \neq q_1.$$

The latter would be a charge-renormalizing ER=EPR model. The former is a charge-preserving ER=EPR model. Hydrogen spectroscopy can constrain the second, but not the first.

4.1 What the hydrogen test actually constrains

The result of Javed and Wilson-Ewing is therefore valuable, but its scope is narrower than a refutation of ER=EPR. It constrains the conjunction

ER=EPR + classical flux leakage + $A_{\text{throat}} \propto s$ + electron affected, proton unaffected + persistent hydrogenic bridge.

If any of these extra assumptions is removed, the bound on α no longer applies to ER=EPR itself. In particular, the argument does not constrain a model in which:

1. ER=EPR is a functor from microscopic cobordism channels to boundary stochastic transforms;
2. gauge charge is preserved as a boundary superselection label;
3. the electromagnetic field is an effective boundary field rather than a primitive bulk flux;
4. composite-system entanglement is represented by a coarse-grained channel network rather than a single elementary bridge;
5. microscopic bridges are transient channel contributions rather than persistent semiclassical throats.

These conditions are precisely the natural conditions in topological 4-geon theory.

Consequently, hydrogen spectroscopy is best interpreted as ruling out a particular semi-classical leakage model of ER=EPR, not ER=EPR as a structural bulk-boundary correspondence. A defensible topological 4-geon version of ER=EPR should therefore make the following claim explicit:

ER=EPR means non-factorizing boundary statistics induced by microscopic bulk topology, not necessarily implying electromagnetic flux loss through a classical wormhole throat.

For study of flux leakages one would need more explicit models of T4G wormhole topologies, not a raw unvarnished GR+QFT account, and to our knowledge this is unexplored territory. Although the ER=EPR idea might eventually prove to be false, in our view it is certainly not yet ruled out by empirical evidence.

To date, the only empirical necessity an ER=EPR theoretical concept needs to reproduce would be isotropic spin correlations [25, 26], and the hydrogen atom spectroscopy in our opinion does not refute this aspect of ER=EPR theory.

5 Conclusion

The hydrogen proposal is a useful diagnostic because it exposes an ambiguity in the phrase “ER=EPR”. If ER=EPR is interpreted as a literal classical wormhole attached to an entangled charged particle, and if ordinary electromagnetic flux can enter that wormhole, then precision spectroscopy and charge-neutrality tests impose severe constraints. But this interpretation is stronger than the conjecture itself and stronger than the version required by topological 4-geon theory.

In the topological 4-geon reading, ER=EPR is not the assertion that classical fields traverse microscopic wormholes. It is the assertion that the non-factorization of boundary quantum statistics is the image of non-product microscopic cobordism

structure. The EPR side is statistical; the ER side is gravitational-topological. They are related by a bulk-to-boundary functor, not by an equality of classical objects.

For this reason, the hydrogen calculation does not refute ER=EPR. It refutes, or at least strongly constrains, an additional flux-leakage phenomenology. A charge-preserving, non-traversable, functorial ER=EPR correspondence remains untouched by the argument. Indeed, the critique clarifies what any precise formulation of ER=EPR must state: the bridge structure responsible for EPR correlations is not a conduit for ordinary electromagnetic fields, but a microscopic topological channel whose boundary signature is stochastic non-factorization.

The spinor and bosonic fields and their entanglement correlations are the algebraic shadow so-to-speak of classical transformation theory after it has been transported into the quantum category of indivisible stochastic transitions between boundary data [4, 6, 30].

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